

Ionic liquids : the new generation solvents[†]

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Manuscript received 3 November 2003

One of the upcoming strategies in developing the viable greener technologies is to replace deleterious organic solvents by eco-friendly counterparts such as water, ionic liquids and supercritical fluids as solvents for synthetically useful reactions. Among these alternatives, the research in ionic liquids has gained impetus over the last decade with greater emphasis on to engineer and make them process-specific. As a result of extensive recent research, thousands of research papers have been reported on this subject. To collate these data as a kind of 'super review' would be a rather difficult task. Furthermore, it will be unpalatable for the general readers. The aspects of transition metal catalysis in ionic liquids, physical aspects of ionic liquids and execution of synthetically important reactions in ionic media have been the issues of several reviews published earlier¹. The scope of the present review is to provide a condensed introduction to rapidly upcoming area of research with strong implications to the field of chemical research. Special credit, however, is given to some papers to acknowledge the novel concepts, particularly the ones which are not reviewed earlier. The scope has been restricted mainly to the chloroaluminate ionic liquids and biotransformations, and the references are selected according to the philosophy that 'more is not always better'.

The term 'ionic liquids' was rather unusual a decade back because of the conventional wisdom that ionic compounds are usually solids unless they are heated at terribly high temperatures. The ionic liquids or more specifically, the room temperature ionic liquids are obviously composed entirely of ions, a bulky organic cation and an anion which can be of organic or inorganic nature. The bulky nature of cation prevents the ions from neatly packing themselves into a crystal lattice as in any ordinary ionic solid. And consequently, such compounds have low lattice energy rendering them liquids even at room temperature.

The first recorded development of chloroaluminate ionic liquids dates back to 1940s when two US scientists, Tom

Weir and Frank Hurley at Rice Institute accidentally prepared *N*-alkylpyridinium chloroaluminate ionic liquid. In 1970s and 1980s, scientists such as Robert Osteryoung of North Carolina State University, John Wikes of USAF Academy and Charles Hussey of University of Mississippi were looking at ways to make liquid electrolytes for new kind of batteries. Several chloroaluminate ionic liquids were prepared by the variation of quaternary ammonium salts and sound scientific data were collected as a result of incessant efforts of these pioneers. The very idea that the variation of cations and anions can furnish different ionic liquids and the millions of possibilities available to the chemists, provided enough room for innovation. This innovation led to the discovery of a new class of neutral ionic liquids which have been dubbed as 'second generation ionic liquids' by Wilkes. The various ionic liquids comprising different inorganic anions were prepared via the metathesis of organic salts with inorganic acids or salts such as HPF₆, MPF₆, HBF₄, MBF₄, TsOH, MOTs, MsOM, MsOH, TfOH, TfOM, HNTf₂ (where M is Na, K, Ag), etc.^{1c}. Wilkes, in 1986, demonstrated the role of chloroaluminate ionic liquids as solvents and catalysts for mediating the Friedel-Crafts alkylation and acylation². Since then, Seddon *et al.* at the Queen's University, Belfast has been exploring their role as potential replacements to organic solvents as reaction media.

'Chemistry in solution' is a concept so old that its history cannot be traced in the past. To conduct the reactions of inorganic compounds in water and organic compounds in organic solvents is a very common and old practice. The solvents provide mobility to the reactant molecules to interact dynamically in solutions. The requirements of an 'ideal' solvent for a reaction process are the broad solvating ability, enough to solvate the reactants and reagents, compatibility with the reaction process, low vapour pressure so as to avoid the loss via evaporation, easy recyclability so as to facilitate the repetitive use without an additional cost to the process, non-flammability, easy handling, non-hazardous

†Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

nature and so on. Fortunately, these ionic liquids were found to fulfill almost all the requirements of the solvent which reaches the functional 'ideal'. They possess astonishing solvating ability so much so that they can dissolve the substances ranging from organic compounds to inorganic ones, organometallic compounds to polymers. This flexibility provides enough room to an organic chemist to play around with these miraculous solvents. They are inert towards most of the reagents and have been employed as solvents for oxidations³, catalytic reductions⁴, base and acid mediated reactions⁵, transition metal catalyzed reaction⁶, biotransformations, etc. They possess infinitesimally low vapor pressure which not only avoids losses via evaporation but also provides a safe working environment. They are non flammable, thermally robust, some of them can tolerate temperatures up to 400° without decomposition (they do not boil; instead they decompose at high temperature). Since they are non-volatile, they can be easily recycled and reused. They are environmentally 'greener' alternatives to the conventional reaction media. Besides these, the hallmark of properties possessed by them is our ability to tailor their properties so that they are best suited to a particular process. Their properties can be altered at will by manipulating their chemical structure with respect to the organic cation, anion and the side chain anchored to the organic cation. Their densities, viscosities, Lewis acidities, melting and freezing points, solvating abilities, lipophilicities and hydrophilicities (and what not!) can be streamlined as per our requirements. All these properties possessed by them in an ensemble have made them the 'solvents of choice' for various reactions. The realization of which triggered an intensive explorations of newer reactions in these solvents.

Chloroaluminate ionic liquids : the first generation ionic liquids

The chloroaluminate ionic liquids or the first generation ionic liquids, are prepared as mentioned earlier by mixing the quaternary ammonium salts such as 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride with AlCl_3 ⁷. The apparent mole fraction of AlCl_3 , N in these liquids dictates the behavior of the liquid as a Lewis acid catalyst. The mole fraction of AlCl_3 , N between 0.33 to <0.5 furnishes basic, 0.50 gives neutral and >0.50 to 0.67 or higher yields Lewis acidic ionic liquid. It is the later variety of chloroaluminates that is useful for driving the Lewis acid catalyzed reactions. The liquidus range (the range of temperatures in which the compound exists in liquid state) is generally between 0.33–0.67, mole fraction of AlCl_3 . The interesting property of these liquids is that they provide a distinctly homogenous Lewis acidic medium for reactions. After the execution of the Friedel-

Crafts reactions by Wilkes *et al.*, several electrophilic substitution reactions such as acylation of ferrocene, chlorination, nitration, etc. were investigated^{1a}. Our group has been involved in exploiting the potential of these liquids for several reactions. We began our pleasant association with these neoteric solvents with the Fries rearrangement. In order to realize the advantages of the chloroaluminate ionic liquids in the Fries rearrangement reaction, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloroaluminate, $[\text{bmim}]\text{Cl} \cdot x\text{AlCl}_3$ ($x = 1-2$) was used as a solvent and Lewis acid catalyst for Fries rearrangement reaction of phenyl benzoates (Scheme 1)⁸. $[\text{bmim}]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{AlCl}_3$ ionic liquid fetched good yields of the products at 120° within 2 h. The variation in the Lewis acidity of the ionic liquid and temperature influenced the overall yields as well as the *ortho* to *para* ratio (*o/p*) of the product formed in the reaction. The extent of conversion of phenyl benzoate was found to be the function of the Lewis acidity of ionic liquid. An increase in the Lewis acidity of the ionic liquid favored the *para* product. The kinetic investigations revealed that the rate of consumption of phenyl benzoate obeyed the first-order kinetics. Higher regioselectivities were observed in $[\text{bmim}]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{AlCl}_3$ at different temperatures.

Scheme 1

We further attempted Friedel-Crafts sulfonylation reaction of benzene and substituted benzenes with 4-methyl benzenesulfonyl chloride in $[\text{bmim}]\text{Cl} \cdot x\text{AlCl}_3$ (Scheme 2)⁹. The substrates exhibited enhanced reactivity, furnishing almost quantitative yields of diaryl sulfones, under ambient conditions. Studies concerning the effect of Lewis acidity of the ionic liquid on the initial extent of conversion of this reaction, reveals a progressive increase in the initial rates of the reactions in the liquids of the compositions in the range $N = 0.58-0.67$, due to consequent increase in the con-

Scheme 2

centration of the catalytic species in the ionic liquid. The interesting insights in to the mechanistic details of the reaction in these liquids were investigated by us with the aid of ^{27}Al NMR spectroscopy.

The Knoevenagel condensation, a useful reaction for the synthesis of electron deficient olefins, was found to work efficiently and expeditiously in $[\text{bmim}]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{AlCl}_3$, and $[\text{bpy}]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{AlCl}_3$ ionic liquids. The condensations of benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes with diethyl malonate gave benzylidene malonates (Scheme 3)¹⁰. The optimized protocol fetched almost quantitative conversions with respect to decay of benzaldehydes. However, the benzylidene malonates subsequently underwent Michael additions with diethyl malonate. This side reaction was more pronounced in case of aldehydes with an electron releasing group at *para* position. Higher molar proportions of the ionic liquid favors the formation of the Knoevenagel over the Michael product. The declined *K/M* was observed as the Lewis acidity of the ionic liquid increased. An increase in the proportion of the ionic liquid increased the *K/M* ratio. The conversions in $[\text{bpy}]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{AlCl}_3$, ionic liquid were relatively

Scheme 3

less with relatively lower *K/M* ratios than what were observed in $[\text{bmim}]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{AlCl}_3$. Coumarin synthesis via Knoevenagel route in these liquids was feasible under ambient conditions. The coumarin synthesis was extended in these liquids via Pechmann condensation route¹¹. The protocol was found to be the most expeditious route (10 min), overcoming the disadvantage of demethylation in case of methoxy phenols, which is often observed in the protocol using AlCl_3 (Scheme 4). A search for the suitable catalyst to induce direct synthesis of sulfoxides from arenes and

Scheme 4

thionyl chloride, avoiding side reactions such as chlorination has been scarcely successful. A useful and advantageous addition to the reported methods was $[\text{bmim}]\text{Cl} \cdot 2\text{AlCl}_3$ mediated transformation¹². The experimental procedure is simple and time saving furnishing diaryl sulfoxides in near quantitative yields within 5 min (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

Yeung *et al.* reported a practical and convenient protocol using $[\text{emim}]\text{Cl} \cdot \text{AlCl}_3$, $N = 0.67-0.75$ for the synthesis of the novel 3-acylated indoles starting with the *N*-unprotected indoles (Scheme 6)¹³. The uniqueness of the protocol was relatively high yields of the acylated products obtained for even the less electron rich indole ring systems. The reaction has been applied to the multi-point pharmacophores of indoles substituted at different positions with versatile functionalities.

Scheme 6

Deng *et al.* reported a novel cyclisation reaction of 1-dodecene to cyclododecane with high selectivity under moderate pressure in chloroaluminate ionic liquid (Scheme 7)¹⁴. It was demonstrated that the solvent due of EtOH and chloroaluminate ionic liquid provides a homogenous catalytic medium for the reaction, from which the products can be separated by merely raising the temperature of the reaction mixture (required for phase separation).

Scheme 7

The use of 1-butyl-pyridinium chloroaluminate ionic liquid for Fischer-Indole synthesis of ketones with aryl

hydrazines has been demonstrated (Scheme 8)¹⁵. The amount of ionic liquid required for the process is equimolar with respect to the ketone used for the reaction. In addition to this, the method does not require the catalyst in high concentrations as is often desirable in the protocols employing PPA and $ZnCl_2$.

Scheme 8

Wasserscheid *et al.* demonstrated the use of the buffered chloroaluminate ionic liquid as solvent for the catalyst, [(cod) Ni(hfacac)] known to produce the linear dimers from 1-butene¹⁶. The dissolution of the catalyst resulted in the enhancement of the activity of the catalyst. The buffered chloroaluminates also take care of the dimer selectivity and product linearity. An added advantage of the method is that being a biphasic process, easy catalyst recovery and recyclability is possible. Singer *et al.* used [emim]I₂·AlCl₃ as a solvent and catalyst for the acylative cleavage of cyclic and acyclic ethers in presence of benzoyl chloride as an acylating agent (Scheme 9)¹⁷. Bifunctionalised α,ω -iodobenzoates have been isolated as the products from the reaction mixture from the

Scheme 9

cleavage of the cyclic ethers.

Our group recently developed a new protocol for the synthesis of *N*-substituted thioamides employing arenes and isothiocyanates in [bmim]Cl₂·AlCl₃ as a homogenous Lewis acid catalyst and solvent¹⁸. Studies reveal that a progressive increase in yields was observed with increasing Lewis acidity and two equivalents of [bmim]Cl₂·AlCl₃ was optimal amount for reaction. A distinct *para*-selectivity for the incoming thioamido group on activated arenes was observed under ambient conditions. The protocol eliminates the use of conventional obnoxious or volatile

solvents such as halogenated hydrocarbons, nitromethane and carbon disulphide. Homogenous catalysis, reduced reaction times, and ambient conditions are some of distinctively notable advantages offered by the novel procedure. Further the ionic liquid, [bmim]Cl₂·AlCl₃, $N = 0.67$ mediated syntheses of aromatic sulfonamides via electrophilic substitution of arenes has been investigated by us¹⁹. The protocol serves as a distinctly expeditious and ambient route towards the syntheses of these pharmaceutically useful compounds, yielding quantitative conversions at room temperature within 5–30 min in most of the cases. The method has been used for the syntheses of a diverse range of sulfonamides by variation of arenes and sulfamoyl chlorides. With monosubstituted benzenes, the protocol offers an added advantage of exclusive selectivity towards the formation of *para* substituted sulfonamides over the *ortho* products.

Ionic liquids : promising solvents for biocatalytic reactions

Almost one and a half decade back when the potential of the neutral ionic liquids as the reaction media was not even conceptualized Adams *et al.* in 1984 demonstrated the stability of alkaline phosphatase in aq. solution of quaternary salt. The authors found that the enzymes were relatively stable in a mixture of tetraethylammonium nitrate and water in ratio 4 : 1 (v/v)²⁰. However with an increasing consciousness regarding these ionic liquids, the enzymic scientists obviously became curious about the behavior of enzymes in these neoteric solvents. This led to a rapid development of biocatalytic research in these ionic liquids as indicated by some of the examples below.

Lye *et al.* came out with the first report on multiphase bioprocess operation employing the present days second generation room temperature ionic liquids as replacements for the conventional organic solvents²¹. The ionic liquid [bmim]PF₆ and water were successfully employed as a liquid-liquid biphase for the *Rhodococcus* R312 catalyzed biotransformations of 1,3-dicyanobenzene. The authors discovered the greater specific activity of the biocatalyst in H₂O-[bmim]PF₆ system almost by an order of magnitude than in H₂O-toluene system. Shortly, thereafter a report appeared by the Erbeldinger *et al.* which was the first report demonstrating the use of isolated, cell free enzyme in ionic liquid. As a model reaction, *Z*-aspartane was synthesized in a thermolysin catalyzed reaction of carbobenzoxy-*L*-aspartate and *L*-phenyl alanine methylester hydrochloride in [bmim]PF₆ containing 5% (v/v) H₂O (Scheme 10)²². Besides, the authors have also demonstrated that the enzyme

Scheme 10

(which otherwise requires immobilization) exhibits outstanding stability in this novel medium.

Sheldon *et al.* demonstrated that *Candida antarctica* lipase is able to catalyze a variety of transformations such as transesterifications, aminolysis and perhydrolysis in two different ionic liquids, [bmim]PF₆ and [bmim]BF₄ in absence of water²³. The reactions were executed with free (NOVO SP525) or immobilized enzyme (Novozyme 435). The reaction rates were comparable with or better than those observed in the conventional organic media. For example, the reaction of octanoic acid with ammonia in [bmim]BF₄ at 40° gave complete conversion to octanamide in 4 days compared to 17 days for the same conversion using ammonium carbamate in methyl isobutyl ketone. The epoxidation of cyclohexene by peroxy octanoic acid, generated *in situ* by Novozyme 435 catalyzed reaction of octanoic acid with

Scheme 11

60% aq. H₂O₂ proceeded smoothly in [bmim]BF₄ (Scheme 11). Kragl and coworkers investigated the kinetic resolution of 1-phenyl ethanol with nine different lipases in ten different ionic liquids²⁴. A variety of ionic liquids comprising of cations such as [bmim], [mmim], [4mbpy] and anions such as PF₆⁻, BF₄⁻, TfO⁻, MsO⁻, BzO⁻ and Tf₂N⁻ were prepared and employed as the reaction media for transesterification of a rac-1-phenyl ethanol. Surprisingly, with the lipases from *Pseudomonas sp.* and *Alcaligenes sp.* the enantioselectivity for the formation of acetate was improved to a large extent as compared to the reaction in methyl *tert* butyl ether (MTBE).

Itoh *et al.* reported lipase catalyzed enantioselective acylation of allylic alcohols in ionic liquids using vinyl ac-

etate as an irreversible acyl donor (Scheme 12)²⁵. The authors observed that the rate of acylation was strongly dependent on the anionic part of the ionic liquid. While the *Candida antarctica* catalyzed acylation proceeded with high enantioselectivity in all the solvents tested, the reaction rates in [bmim]BF₄ were nearly equal to those observed in diisopropyl ether. Similarly, Kim and coworkers observed markedly enhanced enantioselectivities in the lipase *Pseudomonas cepacia* and *Candida antarctica* cata-

Scheme 12

lyzed transesterifications of various secondary alcohols in ionic liquids [emim]BF₄ and [bmim]PF₆²⁶. Upon comparison of the enantioselectivity in ILs and organic solvents, toluene and THF, it was found that relatively lipases were upto 25 times more enantioselective in ionic liquids. In the best experiments the enantiomeric ratio greater than 1000 was observed in *Pseudomonas cepacia* catalyzed reactions in [bmim]PF₆. The lipase activity in ionic liquids was found to be as good as or slightly lower than in organic solvents.

Kim *et al.* further extended the work of investigation of enantioselectivity of lipase catalyzed reactions in ionic liquids. In a different strategy, a new type of immobilization protocol was devised wherein the ionic compound,

Fig. 1

1-(3'-phenylpropyl)-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate (Fig. 1), which is liquid above 53° was mixed with the enzyme in its liquid state and then solidified. The preparation so obtained was referred to as Ionic Liquid-Coated-Enzyme (ILCE) and was used in organic solvents for enantioselective acylation of alcohols. This preparation of *Pseudomonas* lipase exhibited markedly enhanced enantioselectivity in almost all the cases when compared with the native form of the enzyme²⁷.

A newly synthesized ionic liquid 1-ethylpyridinium trifluoroacetate, [epy]TFA was employed by Malhotra *et al.* for the protease catalyzed resolution of *N*-acetyl amino acid

esters²⁸. The products with *ee* between 86–97% were realized in an optimized protocol. The yields and optical purity of the products was found to be better or comparable to those observed in acetonitrile as a solvent. Kazlauskas *et al.* reported an improved method of preparation of ionic liquids, which were found to be more suitable for the lipase catalyzed biotransformations²⁹. The lipase catalyzed reactions that previously did not occur in untreated ionic liquid, now occur at the rates comparable to those in the non-polar organic solvents such as toluene. Acetylation of 1-phenyl ethanol catalyzed by lipase from *Pseudomonas cepacia* was as fast and as enantioselective in ionic liquids as in toluene. Acetylation of glucose mediated by CAL was attempted in ionic liquids since it was found to be almost 100 times more soluble in ionic liquids than in organic solvents. We attempted the lipase catalysed transesterifications of 2-hydroxymethyl-1,4-benzodioxane in two different ionic liquids, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate, [bmim]PF₆ and 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate, [bmim]BF₄ and different organic solvents (Scheme 13)³⁰. The hydrophobic and hydrophilic properties of ionic liquids and organic solvents do influence the lipase activity as illustrated from the results. The influence of the ionic liquid as an additive in an organic solvent on this reaction has been demonstrated. We discovered that the supported lipase and the [bmim]PF₆ ionic liquid was found to be the best combination for the said reaction. The enzymes in ionic liquids in combination can be recycled for several runs without substantial diminution in the lipase activity. We also investigated the supported lipase *Pseudomonas cepacia*, catalyzed aliphatic polyester syn-

Scheme 13

thesis in 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium hexafluorophosphate ionic liquid as a novel reaction medium³¹.

Lipase PS-C demonstrated remarkable compatibility with the novel reaction medium by exhibiting excellent catalysis in polycondensation of diethyl octane-1,8-dicarboxylate with 1,4-butanediol at room temperature (Scheme 14). Lipase exhibited high initial rate of transesterification as indicated from the rapid initial consumption of the monomer, diethyl octane-1,8-dicarboxylate. The average molecular weight of the polymer formed was limited to around 2270 at room tem-

Scheme 14

perature. A relatively high molecular weight polymer was obtained in relatively shorter reaction times at 60°.

Russell *et al.* carried out the solvatochromic analysis of ionic liquids and the partition coefficient data obtained suggests that the ionic liquids are highly polar and hydrophilic in nature in comparison to the organic solvents such as hexane, acetonitrile and THF³². In the transesterifications studied, the activity of free lipase was found to be greater in [bmim]PF₆ than in hexane. The conventional methods of enzyme stabilization proved to be ineffective in hydrophilic ionic liquids. Reversible inactivation of lipase was observed in AcO⁻ and MsO⁻ based ionic liquids, where as NO₃⁻ based ionic liquids were found to inactivate lipase irreversibly. Bartsch *et al.* further investigated the ionic liquid-ScCO₂ combination for the execution of lipase catalyzed transesterification of vinyl butyrate and 1-butanol to butyl butyrate³³. Here the potential advantage of ScCO₂ of differential solubilities at different pressures in ionic liquid was exploited for execution and subsequently product separation. The ionic liquids employed were [emim]NTf₂ and [bmim]NTf₂ and immobilized CAL B lipase on glass wool. At lowest pressures of ScCO₂, least enzyme deactivation of about 15% was observed. Greater than 99.9% *ee* was observed in the enantioselective acylation of 1-phenyl ethanol with vinyl propionate as acyl donor. In different approaches attempted (which included packed bed reactor and continuous flow) good yields of the products were realized indicating the compatibility of the enzyme to the biphasic IL-ScCO₂ system which offered some practical advantages such as easy product separation, recyclability and potential large scale commercial applications. Iborra *et al.* demonstrated that *Candida antarctica* lipase B dissolved in ionic liquids [emim]NTf₂ and [bmim]NTf₂ combined with ScCO₂ displayed good catalytic activity, enantioselectivity and operational stability for both butyl butyrate synthesis and kinetic resolution of 1-phenyl ethanol by transesterification in anhydrous conditions³⁴. The authors suggested that the ionic liquids provide the enzyme with an adequate microenvironment allowing high activity and continuous reuse as

observed in the continuous packed bed reactors. The authors also found that the activity decay was enhanced by an increase in temperature.

Iborra *et al.* carried out CAL mediated butyl butyrate synthesis in NTf_2 based ionic liquids with 2% by volume of H_2O at 50°C ³⁵. Enhanced activity was observed compared to the organic solvents. The authors observed a distinct over-stabilization of enzyme in the continuous operations, which they believe is because of the ionic environment provided by the ILs. Reetz *et al.* reported CAL catalyzed transesterification of 1-octanol and kinetic resolution of phenyl ethanol in ionic liquids using ScCO_2 as a mobile phase in batch wise or continuous flow operations³⁶.

Gubicza *et al.* successfully applied ionic liquids as solvents for enantioselective esterification of 2-chloropropanoic acid with 1-butanol using *Candida rugosa* lipase³⁷. The role of H_2O produced during the reaction and the control of H_2O activity with pervaporation was studied. Under the optimal conditions of H_2O activity the lipase exhibited high thermal stability in IL and it could be reused for at least 5 cycles with only a small loss in the activity. The enzymes displayed much reduced activity in hexane than in ionic liq-

Scheme 15

uid in the repeated runs. Howarth *et al.* reported bioreductions with immobilized Baker's yeast of a series of ketones in $[\text{bmim}]\text{PF}_6/\text{water}$ taken in 10/1 ratio (Scheme 15)³⁸. In terms of enantioselectivities offered by protocol, the method is comparable to those known in literature.

Novel synthetic methodologies in the neutral ionic liquids : a greener solution for cleaner chemistry

Over last two years much emphasis has been onto the design of the ionic liquids by structural manipulations³⁹ so as to make them suitable for specialized applications. There is also an increasing awareness in the community of chemists not only to devise more greener ionic liquids but also to synthesize them in a greener way⁴⁰. Besides this the development of synthetic methodologies continue to be burgeoning area of chemical research.

There has been considerable focus on designing the ionic liquids which could solvate polyhydroxy materials such as sugars. MacFarlane *et al.* reported the synthesis

Fig. 2

of new families of quaternary ammonium, *N*-alkyl-*N*-methylpyrrolidinium and 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium dicyanamide based ionic liquids $[\text{cat}]\text{N}(\text{CN})_2$ (Fig. 2). The ionic liquids are water miscible and have low viscosities at room temperature⁴¹. They are bronsted basic and can solvate the sugar molecules. They were used for the acylation of sugars in absence of any other catalyst added to mediate the reaction.

The ionic liquids 1-methoxyethyl-3-methyl methanesulfonate (MOEMIM.OMs) was prepared by a novel methodology in which the mesylate esters are treated with *N*-methylimidazole. This can be carried out either by direct heating or by microwave heating. The insolubility of nucleosides in many organic solvents is a major obstacle to development of new methodologies. The ether linkage containing ionic liquids were designed with an intention to serve as solvents for nucleoside chemistry. The ionic liq-

Scheme 16

uid 1-methoxyethyl-3-methyl methanesulfonate (MOEMIM.OMs) was prepared and used for the execution of acetylation of various 2'-deoxyribonucleosides⁴².

The enantioselective Michael addition of dimethyl malonate to 1,3-diphenylprop-2-en-1-one promoted by a quaternary derived ammonium salt from quinine as a phase transfer catalyst in different ionic liquids (Scheme 16). $[\text{bmim}]\text{PF}_6$, $[\text{bpy}]\text{BF}_4$, $[\text{bmim}]\text{BF}_4$ as well as in conventional organic solvents was studied⁴³. The organic cation

of ionic liquid was found to influence the enantioselectivity of the reaction. The results indicated that the reversal of enantioselectivity was not due to the PTC but can be attributed to the cation associated with the anion of the ionic liquid.

There is wealth of literature available on the execution of transition metal complexes catalyzed C–C coupling reactions, taking an advantage of the solubility of the catalyst in these liquids⁴⁴. Utilization of grafted ionic liquids and use of supported ionic liquid phase are some interesting areas attracting considerable attention of the chemists now-a-days^{45,46}. In addition to this the focus of research is on to use of immobilized catalysts such as rare earth triflates and other inorganic salts in ionic liquids. Their amalgamation with the other green solvents such as ScCO₂ and water is also gaining considerable attention, to develop environmentally benign technologies³³. There has been a considerable gain in impetus on to engineer them as solvents with favorable attributes.

Concluding remarks

It is now a well established and experimentally proven fact that the ionic liquids are promising solvents for diverse range of applications. With the pace at which the research in this area is escalating, it is not far when they will become common not only on an organic chemistry laboratory shelf but also as solvents in commercial applications. They surely are the solvents of future and are all set to revolutionize the way an organic chemist thinks and works.

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